

CYBERSECURITY THREATS, VULNERABILITIES AND ATTACKS: A COMPREHENSIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. As the digital environment has become increasingly influential in our lives, crimes are also increasingly using the digital environment. Technologies such as social networks, cryptocurrencies, and cloud computing, which are important components of the digital environment, are surrounded by a number of security problems. Over the past few years, cybercriminals have automated attacks, making them a regular job for themselves, and providing a number of services. The use of traditional security systems such as next-generation firewalls, antivirus/antimalware programs, IDS/IPS systems, and access control is no longer enough to reduce the attack load. It is worth noting that today, the development of new innovative solutions to prevent cyberattacks is becoming a pressing issue. This article studies and analyzes cybersecurity problems. In this analysis, the terms threat, vulnerability, and attack are defined as cybersecurity security problems, and their types are presented. This article proposes several solutions for detecting cyberattacks, from which the use of machine learning methods, deep learning, is proposed as an effective solution to prevent a number of possible future attacks. However, it should be noted that these methods are not resistant to evasion and circumvention of cyberattacks.

Key words: Cyber Threat, Attack, Vulnerability.

Introduction

In today's era of rapid development of information technologies, the word cyber [3] is increasingly entering our lives with the concept of virtuality. In general, cybersecurity protects the integrity, confidentiality and availability of assets that are present in information systems or are connected to the electronic environment established by third parties, which are considered important aspects of the three security principles. For example, these assets can include data, devices, personnel, communications, etc., and cybersecurity is responsible for the security of these assets in virtual life [4]. The main goal of cybersecurity

is to protect users, organizations or specific institutions on the Internet and their data. Viewing the security sector as a second level can have significant negative consequences. For example, a malicious person can access the personal profile of a legitimate user through the network and perform actions on his behalf. Examples of such actions include the violation of data confidentiality, modification, destruction, theft [5] or the appropriation of ID passwords and transactions based on material principles such as credit cards, personal accounts. Depending on the extent of the damage caused, these types of attacks can cause serious financial damage to individuals, large companies, and even government agencies and governments. Several years of research have confirmed that most cyberattacks have caused billions of dollars in damage to the global economic market. Nowadays, cyberattacks can be viewed not as computer attacks organized by ordinary hackers, but as large organizations supported and financed by large organizations. To prevent such attacks, security personnel are required to have a well-developed cybersecurity policy.

Today, the security mechanisms that various organizations are developing to strengthen their security policies are no longer considered sufficient measures to protect against cybersecurity vulnerabilities. For this reason, in recent years, developing cyber-resistant defense mechanisms has become a hot and controversial topic for researchers.

CYBER security background

As we get acquainted with the field of cybersecurity, it would be appropriate to first provide the meaning of some of the key terms related to this field. Below are the definitions of several terms:

Cyberspace acts as a global domain in the world of information systems, and its distinctive feature is the use of the electronic and electromagnetic spectrum for the creation, updating and storage of information. Cyberspace, having the ability to use the latest technologies, has the ability to exchange information between interconnected networks, in which it can use the data flow as it pleases [6, 7].

Vulnerability is considered a system or defect in cyberspace that allows an attacker to execute malicious commands, gain unauthorized access to the network, or carry out any threat [8, 9].

Threat is a set of actions aimed at violating security, and is evaluated as an asset that has negative consequences in terms of its impact [8, 10].

An attack is a set of actions aimed at causing damage to a system, using various means and methods to enter an active mode using cyber vulnerabilities.

This article focuses on cybersecurity issues and analyzes the types and scope of the above terms. According to the results of this analysis, cyber threats are classified as follows (Figure 1):

- Computer viruses. Computer viruses are a type of computer program that has the ability to reproduce itself and inherit the operating characteristics of its original copy, and are computer programs that are installed without the user's permission and are capable of changing the way the computer works.

- Computer worms. Worms are malicious programs with a more complex structure. They are usually distributed on various websites, in e-mails, and in the process of exchanging files over the network. The main task of worms is that, after they take over a system, they try to distribute their source files to other users without the user's participation, using the data sources of the user.

- Trojan horses. As the name suggests, this type of threat is a type of program that is downloaded by the user by introducing itself as a useful program. This program belongs to the class of malicious software and may appear to be legitimate, but is not [11].

- Rootkits. A rootkit is a type of malicious software that allows hackers to remotely access and control the victim's device.

Figure 1. Common computer threats

Cybercriminals are developing their attack programs step by step to cause significant damage to computer systems and gain more profit. The type of activity that is assessed at different levels, from attacks such as stealing user data to attacks aimed at extorting ransom money, is also called risk. The most common types of these cyber risks are described in detail below:

- Spyware. This program is a type of software known as spyware, which collects information on the user's computer without their consent. This program monitors the user's behavior, including recording keystrokes, monitoring web pages visited, copying data from the hard drive, and monitoring it, which is used to compromise the privacy of personal information.

- Scareware. This is the name given to malicious computer programs that fall into the class of malware known as "Rogueware" [12]. This type of program mainly forces users to purchase software by intimidating them.

- Joke programs. This is a type of software that does not have any malicious purposes. This software is designed to annoy users, and its main purpose is to entertain [13].

- Ransomware. Ransomware is one of the most popular types of cyber threats that can prevent access to important files, documents, applications, operating systems, networks, or servers [14]. They have the ability to encrypt files, documents, and servers on a network using a single computer.

- Hacking Tools. This tool is designed to intentionally modify computer programs or hardware, performing its functions without changing the architecture and design. The main purpose of this tool is to help a malicious person [15].

- Remote Access. This program allows you to remotely connect to and control a user's computer network over the Internet and works based on specific protocols.

The different types of vulnerabilities are briefly described below.

- Software vulnerabilities: Software vulnerabilities occur when there are errors or bugs in applications, which are seen as opportunities for attackers to exploit these vulnerabilities to compromise the system.

- Firewall vulnerabilities: A firewall serves as a software and hardware defense that protects networks from attacks. A firewall vulnerability is associated with an error, flaw, or miscalculation made during the design, implementation, or configuration of the firewall that can be used to launch attacks on the trusted network that the firewall is intended to protect.

- TCP/IP vulnerabilities: These vulnerabilities are related to different layers of the network. These protocols may lack the necessary functionality in an unprotected network. ARP attacks and fragmentation attacks are examples of attacks that result from TCP/IP vulnerabilities.

- Wireless network vulnerabilities: Wireless local area networks (LANs) are subject to protocol-based attacks that are comparable to wired LANs. Unsecured wireless access points can also be a potential threat because they create an entry point for an attacker to gain unauthorized access to a personal or corporate network.

- Operating system vulnerabilities: These are security vulnerabilities in operating systems such as Windows, macOS, and Unix.

- Web server: These vulnerabilities arise from design and engineering errors or from misuse. Examples of attacks that can be exploited through web server vulnerabilities include sniffing and spoofing attacks.

Common types of attacks are illustrated below (Figure 2):

- Social engineering attacks. When it comes to cybersecurity, most users focus on protecting themselves from malicious actors who exploit technological vulnerabilities to gain access to a network. However, there is another security problem that needs to be addressed, which is the attempt to gain access to a network by exploiting the vulnerabilities of users, and this is known in science as social engineering.

- Application attacks. Application attacks are a type of attack that typically targets the application layer and looks for vulnerabilities or flaws in the code. The success of this type of attack is that any programming language, code written in it, programming language libraries and frameworks do not have reliable protection and a vulnerability or flaw can be found.

- Cryptography attacks. Cryptography is considered one of the important parts of the cybersecurity field and includes a number of factors such as converting open-format data into a closed encrypted state based on certain rules, storing it, and transmitting it. Typically, the main goal of a cryptographic attack is to master the transmitted encrypted data, break the encryption key, or cryptographic protocols. These attacks can be divided into passive or active types depending on the type of action.

- Hijacking attacks. This type of attack is an attack related to the network section of the cybersecurity field, and the main focus is on controlling network communications, computer networks, and software [16].

- Computer network attacks (CNAs). This type of attack is one of the important types in cybersecurity, and the main focus is on controlling computer networks. This type of attack involves disabling, modifying, or misusing systems.

- Phishing attacks. Phishing is one of the most common cyber threats today. According to the internationally accepted definition, phishing is “a type of online fraud targeting consumers by sending emails that appear to come from a known source” [17].

- Malware attacks. Malware is a type of attack software that is designed to seriously disrupt the operation of computer systems and networks, and to cause harm to users’ data in order to annoy them.

- Bots and botnets. A “bot”, short for robot, is a software program that performs repetitive, automated, and predetermined tasks [18].

- Password attacks. This type of attack is one of the most commonly used types of attack in the field of cybersecurity, and is mainly carried out for personal malicious purposes or for some specific purpose [19].

- Man-in-the-middle attack. A man-in-the-middle attack is the oldest type of cyberattack in which a malicious party secretly intervenes in a communication between two parties [20]. This type of attack involves reading, modifying, or destroying data exchanged between two legitimate parties over a secure or unsecured communication medium. This involves establishing a secret connection while participating in the session.

- Denial of Service (DoS). This type of attack aims to make a machine or network resource inaccessible to the intended users.

Figure 2. Types of cyberattack

Proposed solution

When addressing cybersecurity issues, it is advisable to consider a number of factors and use several methods as a holistic solution. Below, a number of solutions are presented to identify, prevent, and evade cybersecurity threats and attacks. The proposed methods are divided into two main categories, which are also divided into categories within each other (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Classification of technical and non-technical cybersecurity solutions

The above-mentioned security tools and protocols are widely used in detecting, preventing and monitoring cyberattacks (Figure 9). For example, ACL (Access Control Lists) focuses on filtering packets based on certain rules based on the source IP address, port and protocol. This security tool is considered an effective solution for detecting and preventing DDoS attacks. On the other hand, IDS and IPS systems are widely used in detecting and preventing attacks in real-time using anomaly and signature-based approaches. It is advisable to use the above tools and protocols together in a computer network as a comprehensive solution to protect the entire organization from attacks. In recent years, due to the development of artificial intelligence and its application in various fields, the use of Machine Learning methods in protecting against cyberattacks has also become a priority. Self-learning techniques allow adding new features to detect new attacks and improve the quality of monitoring. Machine learning techniques are covering a wide range of areas in cyberspace attack detection and prevention (Figure 4).

Figure 4. ML techniques in cyber space

Conclusion

This article summarizes cybersecurity issues and technologically effective solutions. In order to provide a broad coverage of cybersecurity issues, we have analyzed cybersecurity issues by dividing them into three large parts: cyber threats, vulnerabilities, and attack levels. The main goal is to understand the components of cybersecurity and classify them by factors that should be taken into account when developing comprehensive solutions to detect attacks.

Although the above-mentioned protective tools, methods, and protocols have made extensive progress in ensuring data integrity, identifying vulnerabilities in computer systems, secure information exchange processes in communication networks, and systems for detecting and blocking attacks, these solutions alone are not enough to prevent the majority of cyberattacks. Systems for detecting, preventing, and monitoring cyberattacks require a comprehensive solution.

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